

CNR.BiOmics

BIG DATA FOR BETTER LIFE

NextGenIT

Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics

General Aim

To empower the Italian node of ELIXIR, to provide the user community an infrastructure of excellence for Bioinformatics and Integrative Omics with the most advanced platforms for high-throughput generation and analyses of genomic, proteomic and metabolomic data and enhance ELIXIR-IT communities and services

GRANT MUR 33.133.352,5 €

CNRBiOmics successfully concluded without any cost-cutting December 2022

The Omics platforms are now in use.

UNIONE EUROPEA
Fondo Sociale Europeo
Fondo Europeo di Sviluppo Regionale

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

Progetto PIR01_00017

Centro Nazionale di Ricerca in Bioinformatica per le Scienze "Omiche"

Scientific Coordinator **Elisabetta Sbisà**
Financial Officer **Laura Marra**

Total Funding 14.503.877,00 €

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ELIXIR-IT Platforms

The CNRBioMics project enabled the enhancing of TOOLS, COMPUTE and TRAINING Platforms and the integration in ELIXIR-IT of a new Platform for “Integrative Omics” providing the user community with state of the art equipment for high-throughput generation of genomic, proteomic and metabolomic data.

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"National Research Center in Bioinformatics for Omics Sciences"

Proponent

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)

Euro 13.089.662,00

CNR Departement coordinator: Dipartimento di Scienze Biomediche

- Area di Ricerca CNR Bari: IBIOM - ITB
- Area di Ricerca CNR Napoli: ICAR
- CNR Avellino: ISA
- Area di Ricerca CNR Milano 4: ITB

Co-proponents

Università di Bari "A. Moro" (UNIBA)

Euro 809.644,00

Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN)

Euro 604.571,00

Total Budget

Euro 14.503.877,00

High-quality and high-throughput massively sequencing platforms

NovaSeq

PacBio

GridION Nanopore

Single- cell molecular analysis platforms

BD FACSMelody™ cell sorter

10X Genomics Chromium Controller

Complementary platforms for NGS technologies

Bionano Genomics® Saphyr™

Automated liquid handling systems

NGS STAR

OMNIA

CNRBiOmic

Genomic and transcriptomic data validation platforms

Genetic Analyzer 3500DX

QuantStudio™ 12K Flex

Metabolomics and Proteomics Platforms

Orbitrap Fusion™

nLC-MS LTQ XL

ICT Facility
Hardware
Storage big data
Database
10K core – 15 Pb

Empowering the ELIXIR-IT Integrative Omics Infrastructure

O.R. 1 Potenziamento di una piattaforma per la produzione massiva di dati “omici”

Apollonia Tullo Euro 4.410.054,00

The creation of an infrastructure of excellence for the study and integration of omics data (genomics, transcriptomics, epigenomics, proteomics and metabolomics) must have different platforms with complementary performances and was achieved thanks to the acquisition of:

- Ultra high performance massive nucleic acid sequencing platforms, such as the sequencer **NovaSeq™ 6000 Illumina** and third generation direct sequencing platforms such as the **GridION X5 Oxford Nanopore** and **PacBio® Sequel®**
- Complementary platforms to NGS technologies for de novo assembly of whole genomes of eukaryotic organisms and for the study of structural and copy number variations” such as **Bionano Genomics® Saphyr™ System**
- Single cell molecular analysis platforms: cell sorter **BD FACSMelody™**, **Chromium 10X**, **SageHLS** for the preparation of high molecular weight nucleic acid fragments
- Automated liquid handling systems: **OMNIA LH100**, **MICROLAB NGS STAR**
- Genomic and transcriptomic data validation platforms **Genetic Analyzer 3500DX**, **QuantStudio™ 12K Flex system**
- Metabolomics Platforms: **Orbitrap Fusion Thermo Scientific™ LTQ XL™**
- Proteomics Platforms: **TripleTOF 6600 mass spectrometer**

Installation site **CNR Bari (IBIOM - ITB)**
UNIBA (DBBB)
CNR Milano (ITB) – CNR Avellino (ISA)

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High-quality and high-throughput sequencing platforms

Second generation sequencing system

ILLUMINA NOVASeq™ 6000

The most powerful and high-throughput Second generation sequencing system that offers an output up to 6 Tb and 20 B reads in less than 2 days.

NovaSeq platform has a high throughput, but still produces **short sequences**.

Moreover, DNA regions rich in AT or GC or sequences with low complexity and highly repeated (e.g. centromeric regions, regions with triplet expansions, etc.), are not resolved with this type of platform.

This limitation can often lead to incomplete coverage of the genome, with 15% of the genome missing from the final results.

For these reasons it is necessary to complement the use of NovaSeq with third-generation sequencing system as PacBio and GridION Nanopore technology

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High-quality and high-throughput sequencing platforms

Third generation sequencing system

To direct sequence long reads of single DNA molecules with great accuracy and without the clonal amplification step

Oxford Nanopore GridION™

- direct RNA sequencing
- direct detection of chemical modifications of the nucleotides both at the DNA level (eg 5-methyl-cytosine) and at the RNA level (eg inosine).

PacBio Sequel II

DNA - HIFI long reads

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Single- cell molecular analysis platforms

10X Genomics Chromium Controller

Single-cell analysis is of critical importance in revealing population heterogeneity, identifying minority sub-populations of interest, as well as discovering unique characteristics of individual cells.

- Captures up to **100,000 cells** (from up to 8 samples) in < 7 minutes.
- Nuclei suspensions can be studied
- Compatible with **Illumina** sequencers (**short-reads technology**)

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Complementary platform for NGS technologies

Bionano Genomics® Saphyr™ System

This platform provides a **direct optical imaging of the genome to detect structural variations** such as deletions, duplication, translocation and inversions, small structural variations **with a sensitivity as high as 99%**.

It produces **genome mapping data that dramatically improves the assembly of contiguous regions, reduces the required sequencing coverage, and automatically corrects mapping errors based on sequencing data only.**

- **Complete or confirm the large genome contigs or *de novo* assembly**
- **Identify large rearrangements in genomes (SVs)**
- **Avoid the limitations of previous standard cytogenetic methods for clinical SVs detection (karyotyping, FISH, aCGH)**

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Genomic and transcriptomic data validation platforms

Applied Biosystems Genetic Analyzer 3500DX

- Innovative **low-throughput benchtop** sequencing system based on a fluorescence-based **8-capillary electrophoresis system**
- Perform both **Sanger sequencing** and fragment analysis
- **Higher precision to complete or confirm sequencing**

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Genomics

Target Enrichment:

- Whole exome sequencing
- Pre-designed sequencing panels

Illumina NovaSeq 6000

10X Genomics

Single cell "omics"

PacBio Sequel

BioNano Genomics

Oxford Nanopore GridION

Transcriptome

DNA-Protein Interaction Analysis

- ChIP-seq
- ATAC-seq
- Spatial Organization of Chromatin
- Epigenome

Whole Genome Sequencing

- Genome assembly
- Structural variants

Microbiome

- Shotgun Metagenomic
- DNA Metabarcoding

Transcriptomics

Total RNA and mRNA Sequencing

Targeted RNA Sequencing

Small RNA and Noncoding RNA Sequencing

Ribosome profiling

Proteomic and Metabolomic Platforms

**Thermo Scientific
Orbitrap Fusion™**

**Thermo Scientific
LTQ XL™**

**Sciex/Eksigen
Mass spectrometer hybrid
TripleTOF 6600+ coupled to
nanoLC**

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Personnel

Team with specific skills

- follows the technological and experimental developments for each platform
- collaborates in the design of the experiment
- gives useful indications for the preparation of the samples

Staff specifically hired for the activities of all the platforms

CIR01_00017

Euro 1.978.881,60

ELIXIRxNextGenerationIT

Euro 3.006.222,80

O.R. 2 Portale per l'accesso degli utenti ai servizi dell'infrastruttura ELIXIR

Ernesto Picardi

Euro 209.642,00

The TOOLS platform has been strengthened by dedicated software:

- to automate the analysis of large NGS data (WGS, WES, RNAseq and so on) through well established pipelines;
- to facilitate the analysis of proteomic data;
- to improve the functional interpretation by the pathways analysis.

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O.R. 3 Implementazione di una piattaforma di calcolo per la Bioinformatica

Giacinto Donvito

O.R. 5 Biorepository distribuito per la preservazione dei dati 'omici' e Bioinformati

Flavio Licciulli

ICT CNR

Euro 7.472.380,00 (Cloud Computing e Storage)

Euro 685.533,00 (Isola informatica Bari - Milano, Firewall+Router+ Switch)

Total Euro

8.762.484,00

ICT INFN

Euro 604.571,00 (Cloud Computing)

For the analysis, management, archiving and sharing of "BIG DATA", the instruments have been integrated with an ICT platform with high computing power and storage (10K core, 15 Pb storage) with hub in Bari.

The platform will enhance the existing ELIXIR infrastructure.

Installation sites: CNR Bari e INFN Bari (ReCaS) – CNR Napoli – CNR Milano

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O.R. 4 Implementazione di una piattaforma per il training e lo sviluppo di corsi multimediali

Allegra Via

Euro 86.842,30 Computer Training room equipment (instructor's workstation, learners' laptops, projector, printer)

Euro 14.177,71 Equipment for the production of virtual lessons/courses

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The project also provided the enhancement of a high-level training platform to provide the skills necessary for optimal use of the infrastructure.

Applications

- Deliver training courses where needed
- Design and build the ELIXIR-IT eLearning Platform
- Use the technology provided by the PON to design courses according to principles of effective learning
- Offer a portfolio of opportunities to learn bioinformatics online

CNRBiOmics - Big Data for a Better Life

INFRASTRUTTURE DI RICERCA

LifeWatch - Eric: e-Science European Infrastructure for Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research

PER-ACTRIS-IT

CNRBiOmics - Big Data for a Better Life

Il progetto "Centro Nazionale di Ricerca in Bioinformatica per le scienze Omiche" (CNRBiOmics) ha l'obiettivo di potenziare il nodo Italiano dell'Infrastruttura di Ricerca Europea ELIXIR (European Life-science Infrastructure for Biological Information) principalmente nelle regioni del mezzogiorno

Il progetto prevede la realizzazione di un centro di eccellenza per la produzione, gestione e interpretazione di dati Omici (genomici, metagenomici, trascrittomici, proteomici e metabolomici) con sede principale nell'area di Bari.

In particolare, il progetto prevede l'acquisizione delle piattaforme più avanzate presenti sul mercato, con caratteristiche uniche e complementari tra di loro, per:

- produzione di dati di sequenziamento massivo degli acidi nucleici con piattaforme di seconda e terza generazione, anche a livello di singola cellula, e la loro validazione
- analisi proteomiche;
- analisi metabolomiche.

Queste strumentazioni saranno integrate con una piattaforma ICT di elevata potenza di calcolo e storage (10K core, 15 Pb storage) con hub in Bari e integrata con l'infrastruttura ELIXIR esistente.

Il progetto di potenziamento prevede anche il potenziamento di una piattaforma di training di alta formazione per fornire le competenze necessarie all'utilizzo ottimale dell'infrastruttura.

In breve:

Progetto: PIR01_00017 Centro Nazionale di Ricerca in Bioinformatica per le Scienze "Omiche"

Proponente: Consiglio nazionale delle ricerche

Coordinatore scientifico: Elisabetta Sbisà

Responsabile amministrativo: Laura Marra

Finanziamento: Euro 14.503.877,00

Dipartimento CNR coordinatore: Dipartimento di scienze biomediche

Co-proponenti:

- Università di Bari "A. Moro" (Dipartimento di bioscienze, biotecnologie e biofarmaceutica e Dipartimento di fisica)
- Istituto nazionale di Fisica Nucleare (INFN)
- Istituto Nazionale di Fisica Nucleare di Bari.

Documenti

[Presentazione](#)

Finanziamento Euro 14.503.877,00 Azione II 1

1. Potenziamento di una piattaforma per la produzione massiva di dati “Omici”

Responsabile: A. Tullo (IBIOM CNR Bari)

Personale CNR: M. Liguori, F. Marzano, MF. Caratozzolo, S. Giannattasio, C. Musicco, A. Facchiano, V. Carbone, D.Giordano, P. Mauri, G. Longo, M. Marzano, A. L’Abbate, F. Mastrorocco, F. Sambati, L. Bernardo, G. Stea, G. Cananzi.
Personale UNIBA-DBBB: AM. D’Erchia, C. Gissi, C. Manzari, A. Lavecchia, M. De Robertis, S. Cox, G. Visci, E. Notario, A. Amendolare

2. Implementazione di una piattaforma di calcolo per la Bioinformatica

Responsabile: G. Donvito (INFN Bari)
Referente CNR: L. Maddalena (ICAR NA)
Personale CNR: N. Losito, M. Moscatelli, G. Esposito, M. Tangaro.
Referente UNIBA: R. Bellotti (DF)

3. Biorepository distribuito per la preservazione dei dati ‘Omici’ e Bioinformatici

Responsabile: F. Licciulli (CNR ITB Bari)
Referente UNIBA :G. Pesole (DBBB)
Referente INFN Bari: G. Donvito
Personale CNR: N. Losito, M. Moscatelli, G. Esposito, M. Tangaro.

5. Implementazione di una piattaforma per il training e lo sviluppo di corsi multimediali

Responsabile: A. Via (CNR IBPM Roma)
Referente UNIBA : G. Pesole (DBBB)
Personale CNR: F. De Leo, G. Angelini
Referente INFN: G. Donvito (INFN Bari)

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4. Portale per l’accesso degli utenti ai servizi dell’infrastruttura ELIXIR

Responsabile: E. Picardi (UNIBA-DBBB)
Referente CNR: G. Grillo (CNR ITB-Bari)
Personale CNR: A. Consiglio, M. Tangaro, B. Balech
Referente UNIBA: G. Pesole (UNIBA DBBB)
Personale UNIBA DBBB : B. Fosso

CNR - Dipartimento Scienze Biomediche
G. Biamonti; C. Cesarino; S. Salvatore
CNR - Cabina di Regia CNR: M. Rapallini
Esperti MUR: G. Consoli, F. Cobis,
A. Cavicchi, A. Oneto
ETS: M. Morgante

Amministrativi L. Marra, M. Mirizzi, B. De Marzo, A. Armenise (IBIOM- CNR); A. Silvestri (INFN); G. Sabatelli (ITB-CNR); M. Ardito, I. Angarano (UNIBA); **RUP:** N. Montemurro; B. Aresta; G. Panzarini; E. Guadalupi; A. Felici; C. Vanzanella
Staff Area Ricerca CNR Bari: N. Montemurro, F de Marzo, R. Schena

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
NextGenerationEU

Ministero
dell'Università
e della Ricerca

Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

Scientific Coordinator **Elisabetta Sbisà**
Financial Officer **Maria Quarto**

NextGenIT

**Consolidation of the Italian Infrastructure
for Omics Data and Bioinformatics**

Progetto IR000010 -ELIXIRxNextGenerationIT: Consolidamento dell'Infrastruttura Italiana per i Dati Omici e la Bioinformatica” (ElixirxNextGenIT). Avviso pubblico per la presentazione di proposte progettuali per “Rafforzamento e creazione di infrastrutture di ricerca” da finanziare nell’ambito del PNRR” – D.D. 3264 del 28/12/2021.

Total funding : 18.629.475,59 €

Finanziato
dall'Unione europea
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dell'Università
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DI RIPRESA E RESILIENZA

Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche

PROJECT MEETING

5-6 dicembre 2023

CNR ROMA, Sala al piano terra di Via dei Taurini

• Sessione Tecnico-amministrativa

- Stato del progetto: avanzamento fisico, scientifico e finanziario
- Manuale di gestione e rendicontazione di ElixirNextGenIT
- Costituzione Comitato di Coordinamento

Sessione Scientifica

- Tavoli Tecnici
 - ICT
 - Genomica
 - Proteomica/Metabolomica
- Stato di Avanzamento
 - WP1 - Management, Exploitation, Access Program and Integration in the Life Science RI Network
 - WP2 - Consolidating ELIXIR- IT Platforms for better and more resilient services
 - WP3 - Empowering the ELIXIR-IT Integrative Omics Infrastructure
 - WP4 - Enhancing ELIXIR-IT Communities and Services
- Riunione Steering Committee

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Thank you for your attention

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 A T C C G A A T T G C C G A A
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1981 - My thesis
 Sequencing using
 radioactive
 labelling with
 Maxam and
 Gilbert method

**2021 - Scientific
 Coordinator**
 Acquisition of
 high-throughput
 sequencing
 systems